

TAX EVASION AND ITS IMPLICATIONS ON THE NIGERIA ECONOMY

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Abstract

This study investigated the impact of tax evasion on the Nigerian economy from 1999 to 2023. Data used in the study were gotten from the World Bank Development Indicators and the Central Bank of Nigeria's Statistical Bulletin (2023) and analysed using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique. The findings revealed that tax revenue and government expenditure negatively affect the growth of Nigeria economy. Tax evasion and foreign direct investment on the other hand were statistically insignificantly influence the growth of Nigeria economy during the period investigated. Inflation exerted a contractionary impact by eroding purchasing power and increasing production costs. It was therefore recommended that a balanced tax policy that encourages investment, enhance public expenditure efficiency, and implement structural reforms to improve foreign investment effectiveness should be put in place. Furthermore, strict inflation control measures and policies addressing infrastructural and institutional challenges should be put in place to foster sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: Tax evasion, tax revenue, Tax evasion, Foreign Direct Investment, Sustainable Development.

1 Introduction

Taxation is a fundamental pillar of economic development, enabling governments to finance infrastructure, public services, and social programs (Ubali et al., 2024). In Nigeria, however, persistent tax evasion undermines these objectives. The country's tax-to-GDP ratio was just 10.86% in 2023, significantly lower than the sub-Saharan African average of 16.5% and far beneath that of developed nations such as the United States (27.1%) and the United Kingdom (32.8%) (OECD, 2024). This fiscal shortfall raises critical concerns regarding the implications of tax evasion on Nigeria's revenue generation capacity and its broader economic growth trajectory.

The magnitude of tax evasion in Nigeria is alarming, with an estimated \$18 billion (₦13.8 trillion) lost annually due to underreported and unreported income (World Bank, 2024). The informal sector, which generates over 60% of Nigeria's GDP, continues to be a major source of revenue leakage due to its limited integration into the tax system. Moreover, multinational corporations engage in aggressive tax avoidance practices, contributing to approximately \$15 billion in annual illicit financial outflows (Global Financial Integrity, 2023). Despite reforms like the Finance Act 2020, the TaxPro Max e-filing system, and the Voluntary Assets and Income Declaration Scheme (VAIDS), tax compliance remains low, hampered by systemic corruption, ineffective tax administration, and weak enforcement mechanisms. This was evidenced in 2023 when the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) revealed a tax revenue gap of ₦3.09 trillion (FIRS, 2024).

To address these challenges, tax authorities play a pivotal role in combating evasion through stronger enforcement, institutional reform, and technological advancement. Nonetheless, Nigeria continues to lag behind international best practices in tax audit capacity, compliance monitoring, and the use of artificial intelligence in tax administration (Onuigwe, Haruna, & Ekpe, 2023). Political interference and administrative corruption have further weakened enforcement, allowing evasion to persist. This study investigates the effectiveness of tax authorities in curbing tax evasion, evaluating the roles of institutional capability, legal frameworks, and enforcement strategies. It seeks to provide empirical insights and policy recommendations to enhance tax governance, improve compliance, and bolster Nigeria's economic resilience.

Although tax evasion in Nigeria has received significant scholarly attention, critical gaps still exist in the literature. While studies such as Asomba et al. (2023), Abdulkadir and Aliyu (2024), and Usman (2019) overlooked the enforcement capabilities of tax authorities, other research exploring

tax policy reforms and compliance drivers (Sani, 2023; Paul, 2021) tends to neglect institutional challenges like political interference, administrative inefficiencies, and corruption that hamper effective enforcement.

Moreover, many existing studies suffer from methodological limitations, including the use of judgmental sampling or reliance on descriptive statistics (Abdulkadir & Aliyu, 2024; Amos et al., 2019; Onigbinde & Oyedokun, 2023), which limits the applicability of their findings. While some researchers (Olaniyan, 2020; Mvunabandi et al., 2024) have highlighted policy successes, they often fail to assess the role of digital technologies and artificial intelligence in tax compliance tools that have revolutionized enforcement in other countries but remain underutilized in Nigeria. Additionally, state-focused studies (Folayan & Adeniyi, 2018; Jeremiah, 2020) offer limited insight into nationwide tax enforcement issues.

Given these gaps, this study seeks to provide a more holistic understanding of the impact of tax evasion on Nigerian economy.

2. Literature Review

Concept of Tax Evasion

According to Alabede, Ariffin, and Idris (2011), tax evasion refers to the illegal and intentional act of underreporting income, inflating deductions, or failing to file tax returns with the aim of reducing tax liability. Unlike tax avoidance which involves legally exploiting loopholes in tax laws to minimize tax payments tax evasion constitutes a direct violation of tax regulations. In Nigeria, tax evasion has become widespread, posing serious challenges to domestic revenue mobilization and the government's ability to deliver essential public services.

One of the major obstacles to effective tax collection in Nigeria is the country's structural economic composition, particularly the dominance of the informal sector, which contributes over 60% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (World Bank, 2024). A significant number of individuals and enterprises within this sector do not remit taxes, leading to widespread underreporting and substantial revenue losses. This situation is further exacerbated by multinational corporations that employ aggressive tax planning techniques, such as transfer pricing and profit shifting, to avoid taxation in Nigeria (Abdulkadir & Aliyu, 2024).

Tax authorities play a pivotal role in enforcing tax laws and promoting voluntary compliance, which are essential for achieving fiscal sustainability. In Nigeria, the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and various State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS) are tasked with tax collection. However, their performance has been undermined by several systemic challenges, including institutional inefficiencies, entrenched corruption, limited political will, and inadequate technological infrastructure (Alabede, Ariffin, & Idris, 2011; Sani, 2023). These challenges have weakened enforcement mechanisms and constrained the ability of tax authorities to reduce tax evasion effectively.

In response, the government has introduced various tax reforms aimed at improving transparency and expanding the tax base. Notable among these are the Finance Act (2020), the Voluntary Assets and Income Declaration Scheme (VAIDS), and the TaxPro Max electronic filing system (FIRS, 2024). Despite these efforts, compliance levels remain unsatisfactory. For instance, in 2023, the FIRS reported a tax revenue gap of ₦3.09 trillion, reflecting persistent inefficiencies in tax administration. Additionally, Nigeria loses an estimated \$33 billion annually due to tax evasion and illicit financial outflows, largely driven by underreporting, unregulated informal sector activity, and aggressive tax avoidance by multinational firms (World Bank, 2024; Global Financial Integrity, 2023; Abdulkadir & Aliyu, 2024).

Strengthening tax enforcement requires more than policy reforms; it demands institutional transformation. Effective enforcement hinges on the deployment of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, for real-time data analytics, compliance tracking, and automated audits (Onuigwe, Haruna, & Ekpe, 2023; Olaniyan, 2020). Additionally, a skilled workforce, operational autonomy, and insulation from political interference are critical. Yet, political meddling and weak accountability structures continue to hinder tax authorities from executing reforms and sanctioning non-compliant entities, thereby exacerbating revenue leakage and reducing the credibility of the tax system (Paul, 2021; Usman, 2019).

Conclusively, tax evasion in Nigeria extends beyond a fiscal issue; it reflects broader systemic weaknesses in governance. It undermines equitable resource allocation, distorts income distribution, and threatens macroeconomic stability. Addressing tax evasion requires not only strengthening enforcement mechanisms but also reforming administrative processes and improving institutional capacity to foster a more transparent and accountable tax system.

Taxation and Economic Development

Taxation is widely recognized as a fundamental driver of economic development, enabling governments to finance critical public goods and services such as infrastructure, healthcare, education, and social welfare. Musgrave and Musgrave (1989) highlight that taxation serves three core functions: economic regulation, income redistribution, and resource mobilization. In developing economies, where external funding sources such as oil revenues and foreign aid are often volatile, taxation provides a more stable and sustainable means of financing development initiatives (Ubali et al., 2024; Onuigwe, Haruna, & Ekpe, 2023). By mobilizing domestic resources, effective tax systems can support long-term economic growth and reduce dependency on external borrowing.

Despite this potential, Nigeria continues to experience a significant shortfall between its tax potential and actual revenue generation. The country's tax-to-GDP ratio stood at just 10.86% in 2023, far below the sub-Saharan African average of 16.5% and even further behind that of developed nations such as the United States (27.1%) and the United Kingdom (32.8%) (OECD, 2024). This revenue gap has severely constrained the government's capacity to fund its development agenda, including investments in basic infrastructure and human capital development. As a result, public service delivery remains inadequate, particularly in rural and underserved areas.

Low tax mobilization also exacerbates socio-economic inequality and impairs Nigeria's ability to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 1 (No Poverty) and Goal 10 (Reduced Inequalities). Insufficient fiscal capacity hampers the government's efforts to implement redistributive policies and expand access to essential services. Moreover, with over 60% of Nigeria's GDP generated in the largely untaxed informal sector, revenue collection remains weak and uneven (World Bank, 2024; FIRS, 2024). Therefore, strengthening tax systems is not only crucial for economic development but also for promoting equity and inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Theoretical Review

The theories below provide insight into enforcement strategies, taxpayer motivations, and the systemic challenges of improving compliance in Nigeria's tax system.

Deterrence Theory of Tax Compliance

Deterrence Theory of Tax Compliance, originates from classical economic and criminological models, notably Becker (1968) and Allingham and Sandmo (1972). The theory posits that taxpayers act rationally, weighing the benefits of evasion against the risks of detection and penalties. When enforcement mechanisms such as audits, surveillance, and penalties—are strong, they discourage tax evasion. However, in Nigeria, weak audit procedures, inconsistent penalties, and limited institutional oversight diminish deterrence, especially in the informal sector and among multinational corporations. Despite recent policy reforms like the Finance Acts, TaxPro Max, and Joint Tax Board integration, enforcement remains insufficient. Thus, the Deterrence Theory offers a valuable lens for evaluating how Nigeria’s tax administration capabilities and technological tools influence compliance and revenue outcomes.

Institutional Theory of Tax Compliance

Institutional Theory, as advanced by Douglas North (1990), highlights the role of both formal structures (laws, regulations, and bureaucracies) and informal norms (cultural values, trust, and social expectations) in shaping economic behaviors like tax compliance. Unlike the Deterrence Theory, which focuses primarily on punishment and enforcement, Institutional Theory emphasizes the broader influence of governance quality, institutional legitimacy, and transparency. Effective tax systems emerge when institutions are predictable, trustworthy, minimally corrupt, and administratively competent.

In Nigeria, however, institutional weaknesses significantly hamper tax compliance. Issues such as political interference, corruption within tax agencies, and low taxpayer trust in government erode the perceived legitimacy of the tax system. These deficiencies create an environment where evasion is widespread and accountability is weak. Though recent reforms like the Finance Act updates, the establishment of the Tax Appeal Tribunal, and digital tools such as TaxPro Max—aim to improve transparency and efficiency, institutional shortcomings persist. Thus, Institutional Theory offers a useful framework for evaluating how governance quality, bureaucratic capacity, and systemic integrity affect the Nigerian tax authorities’ ability to combat evasion and enhance revenue mobilization.

Capability Theory

The Capability Theory, developed by Amartya Sen (1999), emphasizes that institutional effectiveness and governance outcomes depend not just on laws or enforcement mechanisms but on the actual capabilities; skills, tools, and freedoms available to individuals and institutions. In the context of tax administration, this means that the ability of tax authorities to ensure compliance and enforce laws is contingent on their internal capacities, such as technological infrastructure, skilled personnel, data systems, and operational autonomy.

Applied to Nigeria, the theory highlights how limited institutional capacity evident in outdated systems, insufficient funding, inadequate training, and weak autonomy impairs the effectiveness of tax enforcement. Despite reforms like digitization and the introduction of platforms such as TaxPro Max, systemic constraints continue to hinder performance. This study adopts Capability Theory to explore how strengthening institutional capacity through targeted investments, structural reforms, and human capital development can enhance enforcement and reduce tax evasion. It provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating how the operational readiness of tax authorities interacts with broader socio-political conditions to influence compliance outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Deterrence Theory of Tax Compliance, originally developed by Becker (1968) and later extended by Allingham and Sandmo (1972). The theory posits that individuals and businesses assess the risks and benefits of tax compliance versus evasion through a rational cost-benefit analysis. When the probability of being audited is high and penalties are severe, taxpayers are more likely to comply. Conversely, weak enforcement and minimal consequences encourage evasion (Ya'u et al., 2023).

In the Nigerian context, systemic inefficiencies including lax enforcement, institutional corruption, and underdeveloped tax infrastructure have reduced the perceived risk of detection, thereby fueling widespread non-compliance. This is particularly evident among multinational corporations that exploit legal loopholes and in the informal sector, which often escapes regulatory oversight (Olaniyan, 2020; Ibrahim, 2023). The absence of effective monitoring tools and inadequate digital tracking mechanisms further erode deterrence.

Empirical Review

Folayan and Adeniyi (2018) studied the effects of tax cheating on government revenue in Oyo State from 2011 to 2016. Data from 165 respondents and government sources were used for the analysis and the result revealed that IGR consistently fell below projections due to evasion and recommended better use of tax funds and public sensitization.

Usman (2019) examine the impact of tax evasion and avoidance on government revenue in Nigeria from 2006 to 2015. He used descriptive statistics and regression analysis to analysed the data collected. He found significant adverse economic effects, recommending tax education, harsher penalties, and improved tax administration.

Olaniyan (2020), examined tax compliance and good governance in Nigeria, employed OLS regression with secondary data from CBN and NBS. The analysis revealed that all variables except tax evasion significantly influenced good governance. The study called for increased voluntary compliance, effective tax utilization, and enhanced public trust through accountability. Also, Jeremiah (2020), using questionnaires, interviews, and document review, investigated tax revenue irregularities in Kogi State. The findings linked tax evasion to poor social amenities, accountability, and tax awareness.

Paul (2021) employed survey methods and descriptive/inferential statistics to examine tax evasion and avoidance in Wukari, Taraba State. The study identified complexity, injustice, corruption, and lack of transparency as key drivers of non-compliance and recommended increased openness and public awareness campaigns.

Ogunshola and Kasztelnik (2022), examined tax evasion in Lagos state's manufacturing sector, used literature review and theoretical analysis. Their findings linked evasion to poor training, inefficient administration, and limited technology, and they proposed improved education and capacity building. Similarly, Ashiedu et al. (2022), studied tax revenue and national development in Nigeria from 1999–2020, Using OLS regression, co-integration, and correlation tests, they found a negative relationship between tax revenue and per capita income and recommended increased taxpayer awareness and trust-building measures.

Asomba, Owa, and Onyinye (2023) investigated the impact of tax evasion and avoidance on grassroots economic growth in Nigeria. They employed a descriptive methodology to assess how tax irregularities influence local development. Their findings revealed that tax evasion and

avoidance hinder economic growth by reducing government revenue, widening income inequality, and weakening governance. Sani (2023) studied tax compliance drivers and their impact on tax evasion. Using multiple regression analysis, the research found that holidays, tax morale, and education positively influenced compliance, while deterrence had a negative effect. The study suggested incentive-based policies over punitive ones. Similarly, Onigbinde and Oyedokun (2023) using standardized questionnaires, analyzed tax evasion and internally generated revenue in Oyo State. Their findings showed a strong inverse relationship between tax evasion and IGR, leading them to recommend transparency, accountability, and anti-corruption reforms.

Ordu and Ogbonna (2024), investigated tax revenue and tax evasion in Nigeria: a focus on FIRS. They used a cross-sectional survey with 191 tax officers and Pearson correlation analysis. They found significant relationships between tax evasion and both personal income tax and capital gains tax, recommending stronger enforcement. In South Africa, Mvunabandi et al. (2024), in their study tax evasion and avoidance in South Africa from 1994 to 2021. They employed OLS regression analysis. The study showed minimal tax avoidance and found that increased tax rates positively affect economic growth. They stressed the need for deeper understanding of evasion factors in developing countries.

3. Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research design using secondary time series data from 1990 to 2023, sourced from the World Bank, NBS, and CBN, and employed Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to examine the impact of tax evasion on Nigeria’s economic performance. The study adopted the model of Asomba, et al. (2023) who investigated the impact of tax evasion and avoidance on grassroots economic growth in Nigeria. Based on the theoretical review and empirical consideration, the functional form of the model is presented as;

$$GDP=f(TAXEV, TAXREV, TGEXP, INF, FDI)------(i)$$

Equation 1 can be stated in its econometrically form as;

$$GDP_t=\beta_0+ \beta_1TAXEV_t + \beta_2 TAXREV_t + \beta_3TGEXP_t +\beta_4INF_t + \beta_5FDI_t + \mu_t -----(ii)$$

Where;

GDP = Gross Domestic Product (proxy for economic growth)

TAXEV = Tax Evasion

TAXREV = Tax Revenue

TGEXP = Total Government Expenditure

INF = Inflation Rate

FDI = Foreign Direct Investment

u_t = Error term

Apriori Sign = $\beta_1 < 0$; $\beta_2 < 0$; $\beta_3 > 0$; $\beta_4 < 0$; $\beta_5 > 0$.

Variable Described: Gross Domestic Product (proxy for economic growth); Tax evasion (measured as companies' income tax (CIT) gap); Tax revenue (measured as tax revenue as a percentage of GDP); Total Government expenditure (reflecting fiscal spending capacity); Inflation rate (to control for macroeconomic instability); Foreign direct investment (to capture investor confidence and economic performance)

4. Discussion of Empirical Results

Table: 4.1. Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	TAXEV	TAXREV	TGEXP	INF	FDI
Mean	4.263	14.279	425.363	2.884	18.278	1.562
Median	4.213	12.280	247.234	2.218	12.945	1.410
Max	15.329	44.280	1354.050	9.084	72.840	5.790
Mini	-2.035	0.160	12.676	0.637	5.390	0.200
Std. Dev.	3.901	12.225	421.317	1.980	15.901	1.195
Skew	0.489	0.463	0.980	1.175	2.181	1.881
Kurt	3.495	2.125	2.627	4.011	6.858	6.987
Jarq-Bera	1.708	2.302	5.644	9.266	48.033	42.563
Prob	0.426	0.316	0.059	0.009	0.000	0.000
Sum	144.945	485.496	14462.34	98.061	621.460	53.115
Sum Sq. Dev.	502.063	4931.896	5857755.	129.389	8343.64 5	47.108
Obs	34	34	34	34	34	34

Source: Research's Compilation, 2025 from E-view-9

The descriptive statistics show that Nigeria's average GDP growth rate over the period was 4.26%, with a maximum of 15.33% and a minimum of -2.04%, indicating both economic expansion and recession. Tax evasion had an average value of 14.28%, ranging from as low as 0.16% to as high as 44.28%, suggesting significant variation in tax compliance levels over the years. Tax revenue averaged 425.36 units, with a wide spread between the minimum of 12.68 and the maximum of 1,354.05, highlighting growth in revenue collection over time. Total government expenditure had

a mean of 2.88, but with a skew towards lower values, indicating inconsistencies in spending. Inflation averaged 18.28%, reaching a peak of 72.84%, reflecting macroeconomic instability. Foreign direct investment (FDI) had a mean value of 1.56, but was highly skewed, with some years recording as low as 0.20 and others up to 5.79, suggesting fluctuating investor confidence. While GDP, tax evasion, and tax revenue appeared approximately normally distributed, inflation, FDI, and government expenditure showed significant deviations from normality, as indicated by their high skewness, kurtosis, and significant Jarque-Bera test probabilities.

Unit Root Test

Table 4.2. Results of Unit Root Test

Variable	Test Statistic	5% critical value	Test Statistic	5% critical value	Remark
	@ Level		@ 1 st Difference		
GDP	-3.746	-2.954	-9.498	-2.957	I(0)
TAXEV	-2.761	-2.981	-6.375	-2.964	I(1)
TAXREV	1.747	-2.954	-5.103	-2.957	I(1)
TGEXP	-1.392	-2.957	-9.133	-2.957	I(1)
INF	-2.178	-2.954	-4.644	-2.957	I(1)
FDI	-2.935	-2.957	-6.185	-2.957	I(1)

Source: Research's Compilation, 2025 from E-view-9

Tale 4.2 presents the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test results at both levels and first differences. The results show that GDP is stationary at level, indicating it is integrated of order I(0). In contrast, TGEXP, TAXREV, TAXEV, FDI, and INF are non-stationary at level but become stationary after first differencing, implying they are integrated of order I(1). The attainment of stationarity at first difference, with test statistics exceeding the 5% critical values, confirms the absence of unit root problems for these variables.

Correlation Matrix

Table 4.3 Correlation Matrix

	GDP	TGEXP	TAXREV	TAXEV	INF	FDI

GDP	1	-0.112	-0.230	-0.161	-0.421	-0.035
TGEXP	-0.112	1	-0.605	-0.321	0.195	0.180
TAXREV	-0.230	-0.602	1	0.4702	-0.221	-0.522
TAXEV	-0.161	-0.321	0.470	1	-0.183	-0.342
INF	-0.421	0.195	-0.221	-0.183	1	0.435
FDI	-0.035	0.180	-0.522	-0.342	0.435	1

Source: Research’s Compilation, 2025 from E-view-9

The correlation matrix reveals that GDP is negatively correlated with total government expenditure (TGEXP), tax revenue (TAXREV), tax evasion (TAXEV), inflation (INF), and foreign direct investment (FDI). Among these, inflation shows the strongest negative correlation with GDP (-0.421), suggesting that higher inflation may significantly hinder economic growth. A positive correlation exists between tax revenue and tax evasion (0.470), indicating that as tax revenue increases, tax evasion may also rise possibly due to higher tax burdens or improved detection. Furthermore, the positive correlation between inflation and foreign direct investment (0.435) implies that rising inflation does not necessarily discourage foreign investment, potentially due to other compensating economic factors.

Estimation for Model

Table 4.4: Ordinary Least Square Result

Dependent Variable (GDP)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	11.782	2.441	4.827	0.000
TAXEV	-0.046	0.054	-0.855	0.399
TAXREV	-0.005	0.002	-2.397	0.023
TGEXP	-0.748	0.379	-1.971	0.059
INF	-0.109	0.041	-2.680	0.012
FDI	-0.347	0.639	-0.544	0.591
R-squared: 0.384				
Durbin-Watson stat: 1.502				

Source: Research’s Compilation, 2025 from E-view-9

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression results shows that the model’s R-squared value of 0.384 shows that 38.4% of the variation in GDP is explained by the independent variables, reflecting moderate explanatory power.

The result shows that tax evasion (TAXEV) has a negative coefficient of -0.046, but it is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.399$). This implies that variations in tax evasion do not have a significant impact on GDP, suggesting that enhancing tax enforcement alone may not stimulate

economic growth without accompanying structural reforms. Tax revenue (TAXREV) also has a negative coefficient of -0.005, which is statistically significant at the 5% level ($p = 0.023$). This finding suggests that higher tax revenue marginally reduces GDP, possibly due to the distortive effects of excessive taxation on investment and consumption.

Also, total government expenditure (TGEXP) shows a negative coefficient of -0.748 with a p-value of 0.059, indicating a weak but adverse impact on GDP. This may reflect inefficiencies in public spending, misallocation of resources, or the crowding out of private sector investment. Inflation (INF) has a statistically significant negative effect on GDP, with a coefficient of -0.109 and a p-value of 0.012. This confirms that inflation reduces economic output by eroding purchasing power and increasing production costs, highlighting the importance of sound inflation-targeting policies. Foreign direct investment (FDI) has a negative coefficient of -0.347, but the result is statistically insignificant ($p = 0.591$), indicating that FDI does not have a meaningful effect on GDP within the study period. This could be due to structural inefficiencies or barriers that hinder the effective utilization of foreign capital.

Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.502 suggests the possibility of positive serial correlation, which may necessitate further diagnostic testing. Overall, the findings emphasize the need for a balanced fiscal and macroeconomic strategy that controls inflation, improves public spending efficiency, and enhances the productive impact of tax policy and foreign investment.

Discussion of Findings

Tax revenue negatively impacts GDP, indicating that higher taxes may reduce economic output by discouraging investment and consumption. This aligns with findings by Etim et al. (2020) and Ofoegbu, Akwu, and Oliver (2016), who also observed that increased taxation restricts growth-enhancing activities. Policies should therefore focus on broadening the tax base and improving compliance rather than raising rates to foster growth.

Government expenditure shows a weak negative relationship with GDP, suggesting inefficiencies and resource misallocation may hinder growth. Similar conclusions were drawn by Ajayi et al. (2023) and Alhassan and Imoagene (2024), who emphasized the importance of prioritizing productive spending. Fiscal discipline and focusing on high-impact sectors are crucial for stimulating economic development.

Tax evasion does not significantly affect GDP, implying that tax enforcement alone may not drive growth without broader reforms. This supports the views of Stoilova and Patonov (2012) and Ajayi et al. (2023), who argue that sustainable growth requires integrating tax compliance improvements with supportive fiscal and macroeconomic policies.

Inflation negatively influences GDP by eroding purchasing power and increasing costs, consistent with findings by Alhassan and Imoagene (2024). Effective inflation-targeting and monetary policies are necessary to maintain stability and encourage investment, thereby supporting economic growth.

Foreign direct investment shows no significant impact on GDP, likely due to structural bottlenecks. This is in line with studies by Etim et al. (2020) and Ofoegbu, Akwu, and Oliver (2016), which highlight the need for institutional reforms and better infrastructure to fully realize FDI benefits.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study analyzed the impact of tax evasion on Nigeria's economy from 1990 to 2023 using OLS regression. Results show that high tax revenue negatively affects GDP by discouraging investment and consumption. Government expenditure also has a slight negative effect, likely due to inefficiencies and crowding out private investment. Tax evasion, however, has little direct impact on GDP, suggesting that tax enforcement alone won't drive growth without broader reforms. Inflation significantly contracts GDP by raising costs and reducing purchasing power, while foreign direct investment shows minimal impact due to structural barriers. The study concludes that excessive taxation, inefficient spending, inflation, and unresolved structural issues hinder economic growth. It recommends balanced tax policies, improved government spending efficiency, stronger inflation control, and removal of obstacles to foreign investment. Comprehensive fiscal and structural reforms are essential to foster sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Reference

Abdulkadir, K.S. & Aliyu, S. A. (2024). The effect of tax evasion and avoidance on revenue generation in Nigeria. *Journal of Business Development. and Management Research. (JBDMR)*,5(7),201-214.

- Ajayi, E. O., Giwa, B. A., Obafemi, T. O. & Araoye, F. E. (2023). Impact of tax structure on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Review*, 7(3),10-20.
- Alabede, J. O., Ariffin, Z. Z., & Idris, K. M. (2011). Determinants of tax compliance behaviour: A proposed model for Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, (78), 121–136.
- Alhassan, A. & Imoagene, I. (2024). Tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Financial Research and Management Science*, 4(7),54-65.
- Amos, G., Eric, T. A. & John, A. I. (2019). Effect of tax administration on revenue generation in Nigeria: Evidence from Benue State tax administration. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management*, 7(7), 394-414.
- Ashiedu, I.P., Okafor, T.G., Amahalu, N.N. & Obi, J.C. (2022). Effect of tax revenue on national development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 8(1),50-64.
- Asomba, I.U., Owa, J.T. & Onyinye, C.J. (2023). Effect of tax evasion and avoidance on economic development of grassroots in Nigeria. *Journal of Policy and Development Studies (JPDS)*,14(2),12-23.
- Becker, G. S. (1968). Crime and punishment: An economic approach. *Journal of Political Economy*, 76(2), 169-217. <https://doi.org/10.1086/259394>
- Etim, J., Okon, E., & Udoh, F. (2020). The role of tax policy in economic performance: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa. *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, 55(4), 112–134.
- Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). (2024). *Annual report and revenue statistics*. Abuja: FIRS.
- Folayan, D.O. & Adeniyi, A.G. (2018). Effects of tax evasion on government revenue generation in Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 6(1),76-89.
- Global Financial Integrity. (2023). *Illicit financial flows to and from developing countries: 2009–2021*. Washington, D.C.
- Ibrahim, U. (2023). The relationship between tax knowledge, deterrence measures, and tax compliance in Nigeria. Bayero University Kano
- Jeremiah, J. O. O. (2020). Tax evasion and avoidance by entrepreneurs and tax authority's behaviours: impediments to Kogi State's economic development. *Lapai Journal of Economics*, 4(1), 105-121.
- Musgrave, R. A., & Musgrave, P. B. (1989). *Public finance in theory and practice* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Mvunabandi, J.D., Nomala, B. & Marimuthu, F. (2024). The effect of tax avoidance and tax evasion on the performance of South African economy, *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*,14(1), 52-63.
- Ofoegbu, G. N., Akwu, D. O., & Oliver, O. (2016). Empirical analysis of the impact of taxation on economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(2), 34–44.
- Olaniyan, N. O. (2020). The effect of tax compliance and good governance in Nigeria. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(2), 303–319.

- Onigbinde, A.K. & Oyedokun, G.E. (2023). Effects of tax evasion and avoidance on Oyo State's internally generated revenue. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 6(12), 5963- 5974.
- Onuigwe, G. C., Haruna, A. & Ekpe, M.J. (2023). Tax administration in Nigeria: A primary determinant for effective revenue generation. *International Journal of Recent Innovations in Academic Research*,7(4), 38-43.
- Ordu, C.U. & Ogbonna, F.I. (2024). Tax evasion and tax revenue; evidence from federal inland revenue service. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 25(1b), 480-494.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2020). *Revenue statistics in Africa 2020*. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cea17cbf-en>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2024). *Tax-to-GDP ratios database*. <https://data.oecd.org/tax/tax-revenue.htm>
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2024). *Revenue Statistics in Africa 2024: Nigeria*. <https://www.oecd.org/tax/tax-policy/revenue-statistics-africa-nigeria.pdf>
- Paul, M. B. (2021). Factors influencing tax avoidance and tax evasion in Nigeria: A case study of Wukari, Taraba State. *Journal of Accounting Research*. 4(2):114-126
- Sani, A.I. (2023). Effects of tax compliance determinants on tax evasion in Nigeria: An empirical insight. *ANAN Journal of Accounting*, 12 (2),96-114.
- Stoilova, D. & Patonov, N. (2012). Empirical evidence for the impact of taxation on economic growth in the European Union. *Tourism & Management Studies*, 7, 103–111.
- Ubali, M., Audu, I., & Tijjani, B. (2024). Taxation and economic sustainability in developing nations: Evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Development Finance and Policy*, 6(1), 22–38.
- Usman, M. (2019). The effect of tax evasion and avoidance on revenue generation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science (IJARBAS.COM)*, (1)2,106-123.
- World Bank. (2024). Nigeria economic update: Addressing revenue leakages for sustainable growth. *World Bank*.
- Ya'u, A., Miraz, M. H., Saad, N., Bala, H., Rangasamy, D., Olaniyi, O. N. & Mustapha, U. A. (2023). Effects of economic deterrence theory and environmental regulation on tax evasion: Evidence from energy sector. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 13(5), 289–302.